

IMPLEMENTATION OF INNOVATIVE LEARNING MANAGEMENT SYSTEM: IMPACT ON ENHANCING ICT – SUPPORTED SKILLS

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ABSTRACT

This descriptive correlational study aimed to determine the impact of implementation of Learning Management System in ICT-supported skills among students. Furthermore, it also examined their assessment on the technology-leisure time interest of the respondents and components of LMS. Through utilizing a research-made questionnaire and appropriate statistical measures, the result revealed variability among the responses of the two groups of respondents. The person related information on technology leisure interest do not affect the development of the students on the following ICT-supported skills as to information and communications skills, thinking and problem-solving skills, and interpersonal and self-directional skill. However, these students' ICT-supported skills are significantly affected positively by the components, and process of implementation of LMS. Moreover, there were significant differences on the responses of the respondents on the assessment on technology leisure time interest, process of implementation as to resources, and on the level of communication skills in the implementation of LMS. However, responses of the respondents on the components, process of implementation of LMS as to awareness, application, adoption, evaluation, feedback and monitoring, and respondents' perception on the level of ICT supported skills on information and media literacy, critical thinking, creative thinking, self-direction, and adaptability were not.

Keywords: Education and Teaching; Learning Management System; Descriptive Correlational Design, Philippines